

Partial Molal Volumes and Expansibilities of Sodium Salts of some Fatty Acids in Water at Various Temperatures†

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The partial molal volumes ($\phi^{\circ}_v \equiv \bar{V}^{\circ}_2$) of the sodium salts of formic acid, acetic acid, propionic acid, n-butyric acid and n-valeric acid have been obtained from density measurements (pycnometrically) at 25, 35, 45 and 55°. The partial molal expansibilities (E°) have also been calculated from the temperature dependence of partial molal volumes. Both partial molal volumes and expansibilities have been dissected into ionic contributions using the additivity principle. The partial molal volumes of the hydrophobic anions have been found to vary in the order, n-valerate > n-butyrate > propionate > acetate > formate, and the expansibilities vary in the same order.

The partial molal volumes at different temperatures do not present a clear picture about the structure altering properties of these solutes, but the expansibilities do.

APPARENT and partial molal volumes of both electrolytes and non-electrolytes in water have been demonstrated to provide useful information about solute-solute, solute-solvent, and solvent-solvent interactions in solutions^{1,2}. The existing literature^{1,2} shows that extensive work on partial molal volumes of both electrolytes¹ and non-electrolytes² has been done. However, the temperature dependence work on partial molal volumes particularly of hydrophobic solutes is not that exhaustive and further work in this line is essential, since such temperature dependence studies are likely to provide^{3,4} detailed insight into important aspects of solute-water interactions.

Sodium salts of fatty acids of a homologous series are a set of interesting solutes for studies of hydrophobic hydration. These salts have been studied by a number of techniques^{5,6} but such studies are made mostly at a single temperature only. Hence, for the better understanding of the interaction of these salts with water, the present study has been taken up. It describes the results of density measurements of five homologous fatty acid salt solutions in water at four different temperatures (25, 35, 45 and 55°). The partial molal volumes and expansibilities have been obtained by processing the density data, by usual methods.

Experimental

Sodium formate, sodium acetate-trihydrate (both G.R., Merck), sodium propionate (Boehringer,

analytical grade) were used without further purification. Sodium n-butyrate (SD) was recrystallised from ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture. Sodium salt of n-valeric acid was prepared by neutralising n-valeric acid (Merck) with sodium bicarbonate (A.R., B.D.H.). The resulting salt was washed first with acetone and then with ether and recrystallised⁷ from absolute ethanol. All these salts except sodium acetate trihydrate were oven-dried at 110° for 8 h and were kept in vacuum desiccators for 48 h before use.

Solutions of different molalities were made by weight-dilution method from the concentrated stock solutions in clean standard joint stoppered bottles. Triple-distilled water used, was prepared by redistilling the double-distilled water obtained by alkaline KMnO₄ distillation of deionised water in an all-glass apparatus.

Densities of aqueous solutions were measured with Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometers (70 ml) which were previously calibrated at 25, 35, 45 and 55° using the same water. Six different pycnometers were used simultaneously. The pycnometers with the solutions were thermostated in a water-bath (temperature control within $\pm 0.05^{\circ}$) for 1 h for equilibration. After equilibration and adjustment of the menisci to fiducial marks they were allowed to stand for 1 h at room temperature and then weighed accurately to fifth place of decimal.

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The average uncertainties in the density determination were within $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ which brings the uncertainties in the ϕ_v^0 values within 0.01-0.1 ml mol⁻¹ in the temperature range studied here..

Results and Discussion

From the measured density data at different temperatures, the apparent molal volumes (ϕ_v) of these salts were calculated using the following equation⁸,

$$\phi_v = \frac{m}{d} - \frac{1000(d-d^0)}{mdd^0} \quad (1)$$

where, M is the molecular weight of the solute, d is the density of solution, d⁰ is the density of pure water (the values at different temperatures taken from Ref. 22) and m is the molality of the solution. Partial molal volumes (ϕ_v^0)⁹ were obtained by plotting

Fig. 1. Apparent molal volumes of sodium salts of fatty acids in water against square-root of molal concentration at 35°: (a) sodium formate, (b) sodium acetate, (c) sodium propionate, (d) sodium n-butyrate and (e) sodium n-valerate.

* The limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ_v^0 has been referred to as the partial molal volume (V_m^0) throughout this paper, as they are same (Ref. 4b)

the calculated ϕ_v values against $m^{1/2}$ according to the Masson⁹ equation,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* m^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

where, S_v^* is the experimental limiting slope. An illustrative plot of (ϕ_v) values against $m^{1/2}$ for these salts at 35° is shown in Fig. 1.

The ϕ_v^0 values of these salts at different temperatures are shown in Table 1. The partial molal volume of NaCl at 45° determined by us ($\phi_v^0 \text{ NaCl} = 17.50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) agreed well with that of Millero¹⁰ ($\phi_v^0 \text{ NaCl} = 17.59 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) confirming the validity of the present procedure.

The ionic partial molal volumes in water at different temperatures have been obtained from the partial molal volumes of the respective salts at 25, 35, 45° and 55° by making use of the partial molal volume of sodium ion in water (Table 2) following the additivity principle[†],

$$\phi_v^0 (\text{RCOO}^-) = \phi_v^0 (\text{RCOONa}) - \phi_v^0 (\text{Na}^+) \quad (3)$$

The ionic partial molal volumes and the expansibilities of the anions are shown in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

TABLE 1—PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES (ϕ_v^0 , ml mol⁻¹) OF SODIUM SALTS OF FATTY ACIDS IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

Salt	ϕ_v^0 , ml mol ⁻¹			
	25°	35°	45°	55°
Sodium formate	25.05 ^a	25.70 (1.92)	26.12 (1.74)	26.40 (1.56)
Sodium acetate	39.22 ^a	39.99 (1.79)	40.51 (1.65)	40.90 (1.53)
Sodium propionate	53.38 (1.79)	54.30 (1.73)	55.27 (1.60)	55.75 (1.52)
Sodium n-butyrate	69.18 ^a	70.26 (1.65)	71.45 (1.54)	72.16 (1.48)
Sodium n-valerate	86.20 (1.64)	87.42 (1.58)	88.74 (1.52)	89.56 (1.40)

^aRef. 5.

Values in parentheses represent the experimental limiting slopes.

TABLE 2—PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES OF SODIUM ION IN WATER AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES (°C)

	25°	35°	45°	55°
ϕ_v^0 (Sodium ion) ml mol ⁻¹	-6.9,	-7.0 ^a	-6.5	-6.3

^aRef. 21.

-CH₂-group contribution : The -CH₂- group contribution to the partial molal volume (Table 5) is calculated from the partial molal volumes of two

† Partial molal volumes of NaCl (Ref. 10) and that of Cl⁻ (Ref 11) were plotted against temperature separately and the values at the temperatures required were found out from the graph and finally $\phi_v^0 \text{ Na}^+$ was obtained using the additivity principle.

TABLE 3—IONIC PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES (ϕ_v^0 (ion), ml mol⁻¹) OF ACID ANIONS OF SODIUM SALTS OF FATTY ACIDS IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

Anion	ϕ_v^0 (ion), ml mol ⁻¹			
	25°	35°	45°	55°
Formate	31.95, 32.2 ^a	32.20	32.42	32.50
Acetate	46.12, 46.3 ^a	46.49	46.81	47.00
Propionate	60.28, 59.8 ^a	60.80	61.57	61.85
n-Butyrate	76.08	76.76	77.75	78.26
n-Valerate	93.10	93.92	95.04	95.66

^aRef. 21.

 TABLE 4—PARTIAL MOLAL EXPANSIBILITIES OF SODIUM SALTS OF FATTY ACIDS E^0 ($=d\phi_v^0/dT$) AND OF ACID ANIONS E_{ion}^0 ($=d\phi_v^0(ion)/dT$) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

Salt	E^0 ml mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹		
	30°	40°	50°
Sodium formate	0.060	0.041	0.028
Sodium acetate	0.075	0.053	0.037
Sodium n-propionate	0.092	0.101	0.046
Sodium n-butyrate	0.018	0.119	0.065
Sodium n-valerate	0.123	0.132	0.081

Anion	E_{ion}^0 , ml mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹		
	30°	40°	50°
Formate	0.025	0.021	0.009
Acetate	0.037	0.033	0.021
n-Propionate	0.053	0.078	0.028
n-Butyrate	0.071	0.097	0.048
n-Valerate	0.081	0.114	0.064

 TABLE 5—CONTRIBUTION OF $-CH_2-$ GROUPS TOWARDS PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

	$-CH_2-$ group contribution, ml mol ⁻¹			
	25°	35°	45°	55°
ϕ_v^0 (sodium acetate) - ϕ_v^0 (sodium formate)	14.17	14.29	14.39	14.50
ϕ_v^0 (sodium n-propionate) - ϕ_v^0 (sodium acetate)	14.16	14.31	14.76	14.85
ϕ_v^0 (sodium n-butyrate) - ϕ_v^0 (sodium n-propionate)	15.80	15.96	16.18	16.41
ϕ_v^0 (sodium n-valerate) - ϕ_v^0 (sodium n-butyrate)	17.02	17.16	17.29	17.40

consecutive salts of the homologous series. The average value for this contribution is found to be 15.28, 15.43, 15.68 and 15.79 ml mol⁻¹ at 25, 35, 45 and 55°, respectively.

Previous workers¹²⁻¹⁴ have found out this contribution at 25° for a series of saturated homologous aliphatic alcohols, which was around 16.0 ml mol⁻¹. If we also calculate the $-CH_2-$ group contribution to the ϕ_v^0 from the work of Kaulgud *et al.*¹⁵ on aliphatic saturated amines, it is found to be close to this value (15.95 ml mol⁻¹) at 25°.

The difference in the $-CH_2-$ group contribution as obtained from our work and that from the work

Fig. 2. Partial molal volumes of sodium salts of fatty acids in water at different temperatures: (a) sodium formate, (b) sodium acetate, (c) sodium propionate, (d) sodium n-butyrate and (e) sodium n-valerate.

on alcohols and amines is understandable when we consider the fact that our solutes are 1 : 1 electrolytes, whereas those in the work of the others are non-electrolytes. Further, since the alcohols and amines are very similar polar molecules, the similarity in the $-CH_2-$ group contribution in their case is expected. While comparing their results on amino acids¹⁶ with that of uncharged organic molecules¹⁷, Shahidi and Farrel¹⁶ concluded that the contribution of side chains to the ϕ_v^0 values is not greatly influenced by the terminal charge group. In our case, we do not find this to be true in the sense that there is a substantial difference between the $-CH_2-$ group contribution of RCOONa salts

Fig. 3. Partial molal volume of acid anions of sodium salts of fatty acids in water at different temperatures: (a) sodium formate, (b) sodium acetate, (c) sodium n-propionate, (d) sodium n-butyrate and (e) sodium n-valerate.

(this work) and ROH and RNH₂ (Refs. 12-17) (although OH and NH₂ groups are not strictly charge groups, the situation is not entirely different from the sodium salts as OH and NH₂ groups are fairly polar in nature). Kaulgud *et al*¹⁵ while comparing the behaviour of alcohols and amines have concluded recently that the two polar head groups (*i.e.* OH and NH₂) do make a difference in the hydration behaviour of these two classes of solutes. This lends further support to our contention that the -CH₂- group contribution is different for different classes of solutes. That the -CH₂- group contribution also depends on the geometry of the molecules is evident from the difference of our values from that calculated from the work on various other compounds¹⁹.

Size of the anion: It is expected that as 'n' in CH₃-(CH₂)_n-COO⁻ increases the extent of hydrophobic hydration would go on increasing. That this is found to be so in the present study will be clear if we consider the increase of -CH₂- group contribution to ϕ_{V}° as we go from formate to acetate, acetate to propionate, propionate to n-butyrate and n-butyrate to n-valerate (see also Fig 4) The formate and acetate ions seem to affect the solvent differently than propionate, butyrate and valerate.

Fig. 4 Partial molal volumes of sodium salts of fatty acids in water against number of carbon atoms at 35°.

The latter ions seem to be definite structure makers. Such a conclusion was also drawn by Snell and Greyson⁶ from their enthalpy and entropy of transfer work on these salts from water to D₂O.

Effect of temperature: Both the salt and ionic partial molal volumes increase with increase in temperature. This may either be due to the decrease in electrostriction with increase in temperature¹⁹, or due to the loosening of water structure at higher temperatures. This argument is supported by the fact that the partial molal volumes of sodium formate, acetate, propionate and butyrate in 6M urea are much higher than the corresponding values in water at 25° (Ref. 19), assuming that increase in temperature brings about the same kind of effect as the increase in urea concentration in water, because in 6M urea the water structure is expected to be considerably broken down²⁰, and further

Fig. 5. Partial molal expansibilities, $E^{\circ} (-d\phi_v^{\circ}/dT)$ of sodium salts of fatty acids in water at different temperatures: (a) sodium formate, (b) sodium acetate, (c) sodium n-propionate, (d) sodium n-butyrate and (e) sodium n-valerate.

Fig. 6. Partial molal expansibilities of acid anions $E^{\circ}_{ion} (-d\phi_v^{\circ}/dT)$ of sodium salts of fatty acids in water at different temperatures: (a) sodium formate, (b) sodium acetate, (c) sodium n-propionate, (d) sodium n-butyrate and (e) sodium n-valerate

since electrostriction has been suggested to be less in aqueous urea than in pure water¹⁹.

Since the ϕ_v° value increases with temperature in all cases (Table 1) the temperature dependence of

ϕ_v° values does not give a clear picture about the effect of these solutes on the structure of water, particularly about the difference in behaviour of the first two homologues from the rest⁶.

However, from the values of expansibilities (Table 4 and Figs. 5 and 6) this trend is clear, although qualitative. We do not of course attach much importance to the actual magnitudes of the expansibilities at different temperatures because of their doubtful accuracy. It is to be noted from Figs. 5 and 6 that beyond 40° all the salts appear to be structure breakers. This may possibly be due to the fact that at higher temperature increased thermal agitation does not allow structure formation by these salts to an extent detectable by the present technique.

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